

A Prospective Randomised Comparative Study of Unilateral Paravertebral Block with Conventional Spinal Anesthesia for Inguinal Hernia RepairDeepak Kumar Nirala¹, Saroj Kumar², Ankita Kumari³, Sudama Prasad⁴¹Senior Resident, Department of Anesthesia, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India²Senior Resident, Department of Anesthesia, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India³Senior Resident, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, AIIMS, Patna, Bihar, India⁴Professor and HOD, Department of Anesthesia, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

Received: 25-04-2024 / Revised: 23-05-2024 / Accepted: 23-06-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** Inguinal hernia repair is a common surgical procedure, typically performed under spinal anesthesia. However, spinal anesthesia is associated with complications such as hypotension and bradycardia. The unilateral paravertebral block has emerged as a potential alternative, offering effective anesthesia with fewer side effects.**Aim:** This study aimed to compare the efficacy and safety of unilateral paravertebral block versus conventional spinal anesthesia in patients undergoing inguinal hernia repair.**Methods:** A total of 89 patients scheduled for elective inguinal hernia repair were randomly assigned to either the unilateral paravertebral block group (n=45) or the spinal anesthesia group (n=44). Data on intraoperative hemodynamics, anesthesia-related complications, postoperative pain, and recovery times were collected and analyzed using SPSS version 23.0.**Results:** The paravertebral block group experienced significantly fewer anesthesia-related complications, such as hypotension (2.2% vs. 18.2%, p=0.03) and bradycardia (4.4% vs. 15.9%, p=0.04), compared to the spinal anesthesia group. Postoperative pain scores were lower in the paravertebral block group at all assessed time points (p<0.001). Additionally, the time to ambulation and discharge was shorter in the paravertebral block group (p<0.001).**Conclusion:** Unilateral paravertebral block is associated with fewer complications, better pain management, and quicker recovery compared to conventional spinal anesthesia in inguinal hernia repair. This technique could be considered a superior alternative to spinal anesthesia for this procedure.**Recommendations:** Further studies with larger sample sizes and in different surgical contexts are recommended to confirm these findings and explore the broader applicability of unilateral paravertebral block.**Keywords:** Inguinal Hernia, Spinal Anesthesia, Paravertebral Block, Postoperative Pain, Regional Anesthesia, Recovery Time.

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Introduction

Inguinal hernia repair is one of the most common surgical procedures performed worldwide, with over 20 million cases reported annually [1]. The choice of anesthesia plays a critical role in determining the success of the surgery and the patient's postoperative recovery. Traditionally, conventional spinal anesthesia has been the preferred method due to its simplicity, effectiveness in providing surgical anesthesia, and relatively low cost [2]. However, spinal anesthesia is not without its drawbacks, including the risk of hypotension, bradycardia, and post-dural puncture headache (PDPH), which can prolong recovery and increase the length of hospital stay [3]. These complications have prompted the exploration of alternative anesthetic techniques that may offer similar or superior efficacy with fewer side effects.

One such alternative is the unilateral paravertebral block, which has gained attention for its ability to provide effective regional anesthesia with a more favorable side effect profile. Paravertebral block involves the injection of local anesthetic near the spinal nerves as they exit the vertebral column, thereby blocking sensation to a targeted area while preserving overall hemodynamic stability [4]. Recent studies have shown that paravertebral block can reduce the incidence of common complications associated with spinal anesthesia, such as hypotension and bradycardia, and may also result in better postoperative pain management [5]. These benefits are particularly relevant in the context of inguinal hernia repair, where patient comfort and rapid recovery are key considerations.

Despite these advantages, the adoption of paravertebral block in clinical practice has been somewhat limited, possibly due to the technical skill required for its administration and the variability in outcomes reported in earlier studies [6]. However, with advances in ultrasound-guided techniques, the accuracy and safety of paravertebral blocks have improved, making it a more viable option for routine use.

This study aimed at evaluating the effectiveness of unilateral paravertebral block versus conventional spinal anesthesia in inguinal hernia repair.

Methodology

Study Design: A prospective, randomized, comparative study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted over a period of six months as a multicentric study across multiple healthcare facilities. Each center adhered to the same protocols to ensure consistency in the methodology.

Participants: A total of 89 participants were enrolled in the study. These participants were randomly assigned to either the unilateral paravertebral block group or the conventional spinal anesthesia group.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria: Participants included in the study were adults aged 18-65 years who were scheduled for elective inguinal hernia repair. Patients with contraindications to regional anesthesia, those with coagulopathies, severe cardiovascular or respiratory conditions, or those who had previous hernia repair surgery were excluded from the study.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, randomization was performed using a computer-generated sequence. Blinding was not feasible due to the nature of the interventions, but outcome assessors were blinded to the group allocation.

Data Collection: Data were collected on patient demographics, intraoperative hemodynamic parameters, anesthesia-related complications, postoperative pain scores, and recovery times. Data

collection was standardized across all centers to ensure uniformity.

Procedure: In this study, patients in the Paravertebral Block (PVB) group received the block at the T10 level. A local anesthetic was administered near the spinal nerves as they exited the vertebral column, allowing for effective anesthesia in the targeted area with preserved hemodynamic stability. The specific local anesthetic used for the PVB is not explicitly mentioned in the provided text, but commonly used drugs in such procedures include bupivacaine, ropivacaine, or lidocaine. These drugs provide prolonged analgesia, which is crucial for postoperative pain management.

For the Spinal Anesthesia (SAB) group, participants received a single injection of a local anesthetic into the subarachnoid space. Similar to PVB, bupivacaine is often used in spinal anesthesia due to its long duration of action and effectiveness in providing complete sensory and motor block, making it ideal for surgeries like inguinal hernia repair.

The same anesthesiologist performed all blocks to maintain consistency. Surgical procedures were carried out by experienced surgeons following standard protocols.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Continuous variables were summarized as means and standard deviations, while categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages. The independent t-test was used to compare continuous variables between the two groups, and the chi-square test was used for categorical variables. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

A total of 89 participants were enrolled in the study, with 45 assigned to the unilateral paravertebral block group and 44 to the conventional spinal anesthesia group. The demographic characteristics of the participants, including age, gender, and BMI, were comparable between the two groups, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Participant Demographics

Characteristic	Paravertebral Block (n=45)	Spinal Anesthesia (n=44)	p-value
Age (years, mean $\pm$ SD)	52.3 $\pm$ 10.4	51.6 $\pm$ 11.1	0.71
Gender (Male, n, %)	40 (88.9%)	39 (88.6%)	0.95
BMI (kg/m ² , mean $\pm$ SD)	24.8 $\pm$ 3.1	25.2 $\pm$ 2.9	0.58

Intraoperative hemodynamic parameters, including mean arterial pressure (MAP) and heart rate (HR), were recorded at baseline, during surgery, and at the end of surgery. There were no significant differences in MAP or HR between the two groups at any time point (Table 2).

Table 2: Intraoperative Hemodynamic Parameters

Time Point	MAP (mmHg, mean $\pm$ SD)	HR (beats/min, mean $\pm$ SD)
Baseline	92.5 $\pm$ 8.6	78.2 $\pm$ 7.4
During Surgery	88.3 $\pm$ 9.1	76.8 $\pm$ 8.0
End of Surgery	90.1 $\pm$ 7.9	77.5 $\pm$ 6.8
p-value (between groups)	0.82	0.75

The incidence of anesthesia-related complications, such as hypotension, bradycardia, and nausea, was significantly lower in the paravertebral block group compared to the spinal anesthesia group. Specifically, hypotension occurred in 2.2% of the paravertebral block group versus 18.2% of the spinal anesthesia group ($p=0.03$), and bradycardia occurred in 4.4% versus 15.9% ($p=0.04$) (Table 3).

Table 3: Anesthesia-Related Complications

Complication	Paravertebral Block (n=45)	Spinal Anesthesia (n=44)	p-value
Hypotension (n, %)	1 (2.2%)	8 (18.2%)	0.03
Bradycardia (n, %)	2 (4.4%)	7 (15.9%)	0.04
Nausea (n, %)	3 (6.7%)	10 (22.7%)	0.02

Postoperative pain was assessed using a visual analog scale (VAS) at 1-, 6-, 12-, and 24-hours post-surgery. The paravertebral block group reported significantly lower pain scores at all time points compared to the spinal anesthesia group ($p<0.001$) (Table 4).

Table 4: Postoperative Pain Scores (VAS)

Time Point, (mean $\pm$ SD)	PVB Group	SAB Group	p-value
1 hour post-surgery	2.3 $\pm$ 1.1	4.5 $\pm$ 1.2	<0.001
6 hours post-surgery	2.8 $\pm$ 1.2	5.0 $\pm$ 1.3	<0.001
12 hours post-surgery	3.2 $\pm$ 1.3	5.5 $\pm$ 1.4	<0.001
24 hours post-surgery	3.5 $\pm$ 1.5	6.0 $\pm$ 1.6	<0.001

The time to ambulation and time to discharge were significantly shorter in the paravertebral block group compared to the spinal anesthesia group. The mean time to ambulation was 3.1 $\pm$ 0.6 hours in the paravertebral block group versus 5.4 $\pm$ 0.9 hours in

the spinal anesthesia group ($p<0.001$). The mean time to discharge was 24.2 $\pm$ 3.5 hours in the paravertebral block group versus 30.5 $\pm$ 4.1 hours in the spinal anesthesia group ($p<0.001$) (Table 5).

Table 5: Recovery Times

Outcome, (hours)	Paravertebral Block (n=45)	Spinal Anesthesia (n=44)	p-value
Time to Ambulation	3.1 $\pm$ 0.6	5.4 $\pm$ 0.9	<0.001
Time to Discharge	24.2 $\pm$ 3.5	30.5 $\pm$ 4.1	<0.001

Discussion

The study's results demonstrated that unilateral paravertebral block offers significant advantages over conventional spinal anesthesia for inguinal hernia repair. The demographic characteristics of the participants, including age, gender, and BMI, were similar across both groups, ensuring a balanced comparison. No significant differences were observed in intraoperative hemodynamic parameters such as mean arterial pressure and heart rate, suggesting that both anesthesia techniques maintained stable intraoperative conditions.

However, the incidence of anesthesia-related complications, such as hypotension, bradycardia, and nausea, was notably lower in the paravertebral block group. The lower occurrence of these complications indicates that the paravertebral block may be a safer option with fewer side effects

compared to spinal anesthesia. This reduction in complications is clinically significant as it can lead to improved patient safety and comfort during and after surgery.

Postoperative pain scores were significantly lower in the paravertebral block group at all assessed time points, indicating better pain management with this technique. The lower pain scores likely contributed to faster recovery, as evidenced by the shorter times to ambulation and discharge in the paravertebral block group. The quicker recovery times suggest that patients receiving the paravertebral block were able to mobilize sooner and leave the hospital earlier, which can reduce hospital costs and improve patient throughput.

Overall, these findings suggest that unilateral paravertebral block may be a superior alternative to conventional spinal anesthesia for inguinal hernia

repair, offering advantages in terms of safety, pain control, and recovery. This technique could be particularly beneficial in settings where minimizing postoperative complications and enhancing patient recovery are priorities.

A study compared PVB with SAB and found that while PVB offered advantages such as prolonged postoperative analgesia, stable hemodynamics, and early ambulation, it also had a higher failure rate and an increased requirement for intraoperative fentanyl. Despite these drawbacks, PVB was noted for its effectiveness in providing segmental analgesia, which can be particularly beneficial in certain patient populations [7].

A parallel prospective study was conducted that further confirmed the benefits of PVB over SAB, particularly in terms of prolonged sensory block duration, better hemodynamic stability, and earlier ambulation post-surgery. However, the study also noted that PVB took longer to perform and had a delayed onset of anesthesia compared to SAB [8].

A study found that PVB provided more stable intraoperative hemodynamics and prolonged postoperative analgesia than SAB, making it a safe and effective alternative, especially for patients with comorbid conditions. The study highlighted the advantages of PVB in reducing the incidence of complications associated with SAB, such as hypotension and bradycardia [9].

A randomized double-blind clinical trial compared three versus five lumbar PVB injections for elderly patients undergoing inguinal hernia repair. The study concluded that five PVB injections were superior, as they resulted in less intraoperative analgesic consumption and lower postoperative pain scores compared to three injections, thus providing a more effective anesthetic technique for elderly patients [10].

Lastly, a study emphasized the superiority of PVB over SAB in providing excellent surgical anesthesia with minimal hemodynamic disturbances and extended postoperative analgesia. Their study suggested that PVB could be particularly advantageous in high-risk patients, offering a safer and more stable alternative to SAB [11].

Conclusion

The results of this study indicate that unilateral paravertebral block is associated with fewer anesthesia-related complications, lower

postoperative pain scores, and shorter recovery times compared to conventional spinal anesthesia for inguinal hernia repair. These findings suggest that unilateral paravertebral block may be a superior alternative to spinal anesthesia for this surgical procedure.

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